

Apparent Molal Volumes of some Common Salts in Acetone-water Mixture

K. SINGH*
Chemistry Department, B. S. N. V. Degree College, Lucknow, (U.P.), (India) and
P. P. SINHA
Lucknow Christian College, Lucknow, (U.P.)

Manuscript received 1 February 1977, accepted 17 March 1977

Dependence of apparent molal volume, ϕ_v , on composition of mixture have been examined using acetone-water mixtures as media of varying dielectric constant. The results indicate that the plots of ϕ_v vs \sqrt{c} are almost straight line and have a positive slope for all the salts in all the mixture. The limiting apparent molal volume, ϕ° , obtained in the usual manner is found to be dependent on the solvent composition. The experimental results are expressed in terms of ion-solvent and ion-ion interactions together with role of dielectric constant of the medium.

IN continuation of our previous studies¹⁻⁵, the present work was undertaken to determine the effect of concentration and solvent composition on the apparent molal volumes, ϕ_v , of ammonium chloride, ammonium bromide and ammonium nitrate in 9.64%, 19.84% and 34.43% acetone-water mixtures at 25°. No previous work has been reported on the apparent molal volumes of these salts in acetone-water mixtures, although little work has been reported on apparent molal volumes in some other mixed solvents⁶⁻¹⁰.

This is the aim of present work to use acetone-water mixture for examining the effect of dielectric constant and solvent composition on the apparent and limiting apparent molal volumes.

Experimental

The B. D. H. (A. R.) samples of common electrolytes were purified by repeated crystallisation from conductivity water. The purified samples were dried in a hot air oven and stored in vacuum desiccator.

Water used in all measurements was prepared by redistillation of distilled water containing a little potassium permanganate through block of condenser and having only middle fraction. The specific conductance of the sample used was $1.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at 25°. B. D. H. (A. R.) acetone was first distilled and middle part was collected. After keeping for 12 hours over potassium permanganate, the middle part was redistilled. The new distillate was kept overnight over anhydrous potassium carbonate and was redistilled, the purity of the sample was checked by density and refractive index measurements.

Stock solutions of acetone-water mixtures were prepared by calculating required volume using

*To whom all correspondence may be addressed.

density data in a water thermostat running at $25 \pm 0.005^\circ$. All solutions were prepared on molal basis.

The densities of the solutions were determined using dilatometer described in earlier communication⁴. Duplicate measurements was made for each solution and the average value is taken.

From the density data, apparent molal volume, ϕ_v , was calculated using the equation namely.

$$\phi_v = \frac{1000(d_0 - d)}{md d_0} + \frac{M}{d}$$

Where d_0 and d are the density of solvent and solution respectively, m is the molality of the solution, M is the molecular weight of the salt.

ϕ_v values were determined for each salt in each solvent composition over a concentration range of 0.1 to 0.4 m.

Results and Discussion

From the apparent molal volume, ϕ_v , values for different common salts in different acetone-water mixtures at 25°, ϕ_v vs. \sqrt{c} curves have been drawn. An illustrative example of the plots are demonstrated for NH_4Cl in Fig. 1. These curves are almost straight lines and so the Masson's equation namely,

$$\phi_v = \phi^\circ + S\sqrt{c}$$

appears to be valid within the concentration range studied here. The slope, S_v , of ϕ_v vs \sqrt{c} curves for all the salts in all the mixtures under investigation is positive as reported in aqueous solution¹¹ and methanol-water mixture⁵.

As the present data correspond to higher concentrations, it is not possible to use the data for testing the applicability of the Debye-Huckel limiting

Fig. 1

law. It appears, therefore, reasonable not to attach too much quantitative significance to the S_v values and only dependence of apparent molal volume on concentration and composition should be used to throw light on the mode of ion-solvent and ion-ion interactions in acetone-water mixtures.

The positive slope of $\phi^0 v$ vs. \sqrt{c} curves may be taken to be due to electrostatic ion-ion interaction which is enhanced in a medium of lower dielectric constant. The greatest value of $\phi^0 v$ in most concentrated solution indicates that extent of solvation for an individual ion is least due to increase in number of ions.

The limiting apparent molal volumes, ϕ^0 , obtained by extrapolating $\phi^0 v$ vs. \sqrt{c} curves of NH_4Cl , NH_4Br and NH_4NO_3 in different acetone-water mixtures are given in Table 1. From Table 1, it may be noted that ϕ^0 decreases with increase in the acetone contents of the mixture, which may be due to structuredness of water probably as result of hydrophobic interaction between acetone and water.

TABLE-1 LIMITING APPARENT MOLAL VOLUME, ϕ^0 , OF SOME SALTS IN ACETONE-WATER MIXTURES AT 25°

Percent (by weight) of acetone in the mixture	ϕ^0 in ml mole ⁻¹ for		
	NH_4Cl	NH_4Br	NH_4NO_3
9.64 ($\epsilon_{25^\circ}=73.28$)	34.80	42.30	47.15
19.80 ($\epsilon_{25^\circ}=67.73$)	34.25	41.70	46.60
34.43 ($\epsilon_{25^\circ}=59.17$)	33.75	40.95	46.00

From Table 1, it is also clear that dielectric constant of the mixed solvent decreases with increase in acetone content of the mixture. The limiting apparent molal volume, ϕ^0 , decreases with decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium. This

decreasing trend appears reasonable since ionic association is favoured in the medium of lower dielectric constant and replacement of two ionic species by one.

Thus the general conclusion from the present study is that the smaller dielectric constant favours a smaller value of limiting apparent molal volume, ϕ^0 , as a result of weaker electrostatic ion-solvent interaction. With respect to have a more clear idea of dependence of ϕ^0 on composition of the solvent and dielectric constant of the medium, further investigations are in progress.

Acknowledgements

Authors wish to express their thanks to Shri M.N. Pandey Principal, B. S. N. V. Degree College, Lucknow for help and encouragement. One of the authors (PPS) wishes to express his sincere appreciation to the help and encouragement, he has received from Dr. S. P. Tewarson, Principal, Lucknow Christian College and Dr. W. E. Bauer, Head of the Chemistry Department. Financial assistance given by the State Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (SCSIR), U. P. and U. G. C. is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. R. Gopal and K. Singh, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, 75, 219
2. R. Gopal, M. A. Siddiqi and K. Singh, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, 75, 7.
3. R. Gopal and K. Singh, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1974, 19, 98.
4. K. Singh, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 51.

SINGH & SINGHA : APPARENT VOLUMES OF SOME COMMON SALTS IN ACETONE-WATER MIXTURE

5. K. Singh, D. N. Bajpai and B. K. Dwivedi, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, (In press).
6. D. Fennel Evans and P. Gardan, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, 73, 158.
7. D. Fennel Evans and P. Gardan, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, 72, 9.
8. R. L. Kay and D. Fennel Evans, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, 69, 4216.
9. B. R. Cho, *J. Korean. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 15, 95.
10. J. Padova, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, 39, 2599.
11. H. S. Harned and B. B. Owens, "Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions", Reinhold Publishing Corporation, New York, 1958.